

The African Philosophy of Ubuntu: Possible Driving Force, Ethical Leadership and Good Governance, South Africa's Local Government Sector

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The Scholastic trail within the interface of ethics and leadership has dwelt much on the right and wrong that have emerged from the unethical practices and challenges within the public sector, which we agree has become a significant global issue, contributing to poor governance. The current spate of unethical practices and corruption scandals affecting both the private and public sectors has garnered attention to this paper, as it undermines public confidence in the people of South Africa. The researchers of this paper argue that without ubuntu among leaders, it is likely to lead to a poor working relationship, unethical practices, and poor governance. Leaders who practice *Ubuntu* will be more interested in the well-being of followers, as these are people responsible for the implementation of organizational objectives. There have been studies on ethical leadership; however, the majority of these studies were aimed at professionalizing service delivery and overlooking the concept of *ubuntu* values among leaders and followers. Therefore, this study takes the liberty to correct the shortcomings as it attempts to use the African Philosophy of Ubuntu as a possible antidote to moral problems, which gives birth to poor working relationships between the leader and followers, leading to poor governance and unethical practices, which ultimately jeopardizes the delivery of public service. The engine of this paper is empirical and has highlighted major patterns that lead to the above-mentioned challenges. Paucity speaking on literature has mainly established a paradigm shift in the argument between epistemologies' lens of *Ubuntu* philosophy, that failure to practice the indigeneity lens of Ubuntu values will leave us with the above-mentioned challenges. The researchers concluded with a recommendation that the African Philosophy of Ubuntu, as a possible antidote, be adopted as it is one of the concepts that is always overlooked, and it carries more weight to enhance good working relationships between leaders and followers, ethical leadership and good governance.

Keywords: African philosophy of ubuntu, ethical leadership, good governance

Ubuntu is crucial for positive societal change in Africa, particularly by embedding humanity and care by those entrusted with the responsibility to govern, to lead followers, and to foster good governance. Therefore, leaders should demonstrate Ubuntu, humanity, integrity, and inaccountability, and further incline themselves to ethical climates that nurture good working relationships between followers. Accordingly, to Nkambule (2023-187), the practices of a leader who has ubuntu enhance knowledge-sharing behavior, which is associated deeply with an atmosphere of trust, interdependence, and mutual respect between followers and the leader. Ruano, Schurig, and Wittmann (2021:01) share the same sentiment that the "effectiveness" of the operational process is in adequately promoting high delivery standards and knowledge

sharing behavior among stakeholders. Therefore, this implies that if we are aiming at promoting good governance through a good relationship between a leader and the followers, we should not doubt the concept of ubuntu, as it is a critical aspect that should be combined with the lens of ethical leadership. In a mutual context, there is a need to uphold the African ubuntu values, as exemplified by leaders like Nelson Mandela and Julius Nyerere. Bhengu (1996:4) who indicated the fact that there is no African person without a sense of belonging, which has been given birth by the philosophy of Ubuntu-Botho, which harbors the values and norms passed to them during their childhood. Mpofo (2002) defines Ubuntu as a prehistoric way of life that aims to unleash the greater good in every person by orienting them towards an ethical approach to engaging one another. Teffo (1996:98) with a similar context, states that people are social beings who work towards a common goal to learn from each other, and should all embrace care and understanding, and a sharing attitude in their daily lives. In this article, the African philosophy of Ubuntu is studied to underscore that this theory lies within the purview of the efficiency and effectiveness between the leader and followers. Therefore, while the voluminous trail of literature about ethical leadership (Cheteni & Shindika, 2017; Mpofo & Sithole, 2021; Ngubani & Makua, 2021; Sebola, Moloto, & Mamabolo, 2024) has documented challenges relating to ethical leadership, it consequently neglects the fact that there is a pertinent knowledge gap that is affecting the working relationship between the leader and followers in context. This article sought to use the African philosophy of ubuntu to enhance a

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proactive working relationship between the leader and followers; this philosophy rejects unethical practices, poor working relationships, and a lack of humanity. Lastly, this is a possible antidote for ensuring ethical leadership for leaders. Therefore, in terms of the mapping of this study, the researchers will commence fueling the theoretical understanding, which is discussed below.

Method

The engine of this study is driven by qualitative research, informed by non-empirical study tools such as existing literature materials. The referred material includes books, online articles, academic research journals and lastly, the scholar's views and reports. Qualitative research, described by Bryman (1984:78) is a research method that is deemed to be much more flexible than quantitative research. We cite the view by Mason (2005:1) that through qualitative methods, a wide range of dimensions of the social world is explored, including the everyday life, understandings, experiences, and thoughts of social participants. The statement of inquiry is based on using Ubuntu as the primary source of hope for this study; in so saying, using this research method will help the researchers to arrive at findings by viewing what other scholars have referred to and their perceptions and views. In the sense that this method has helped us to arrive at a systematic answer to the question of this study, to solve the moral problem. It was also important to cite Goodwin (2009: 134) that reliability is important as it enables one to have some confidence that the measure taken is close to the true measure. Therefore, to answer the validity part of this study, the researchers have cross-checked the validity to ensure quality assurance of the theoretical support of this study.

Review of Research Synthesis

This part reviews the existing literature that is important to this study, as it helps to cover the key points of this study the general importance of using the African philosophy of *Ubuntu* as an important tool to ensure ethical leadership and good governance in local government. Furthermore, this section will also cover the challenges that other scholars have highlighted from a local government perspective.

South African Ethical Leadership Challenges in Local Government

Naidoo (2013:655) states that since the new dispensation in 1994, for the era of South African government administration, it made numerous legislative changes for an anti-corruption framework; however, despite such processes, South Africa continues to experience unethical practices and conduct by those entrusted with the responsibility to govern. Therefore, in this study, we remind ourselves that the achievements and the success of each country are judged by the delivery of public service, together with the positive media outbreaks of its performance on matters concerning service delivery. Ethical practices across many offices within local government are concerned with ethical conduct and good governance. The unethical leadership in the public sector affects the entire country, causing problems in the delivery of public services harshly in local government, as the closest government to the people of South Africa is the one affected the most. If we let unethical leadership persist in growing, this will undermine fundamental human rights, including the right to freedom. The service delivers review volume 14 No.2 of 2021, presented by Professor Sangweni,

articulated that corruption is a root cause of unethical leadership, and this continues to impact government institutions' ability to deliver adequate service to the public. In so saying, unethical leadership remains problematic at all government levels, with recent demonstrations and instability against local government service delivery illustrating the extent of public dissatisfaction. Agbude (2013: 10-11) noted that scholars argue that corruption at the grassroots level from ethical leaders is not endemic to a given society or state. Therefore, we understand that local government, as the third sphere of government, is closest to the people and it receives the most public attention, as it is accessible for walk-ins. Thus, we cannot afford the challenges as mentioned earlier, to undermine the effectiveness of the local government in service delivery.”

We therefore cite Saul, Mlambo, and Shapola (2023:551) who correctly cited (Kanyane, 2014) stating that despite means and effect, service delivery is still the biggest challenge that the government faces, and this is driven by the lack of accountability within the public sector. The commitment to achieving sound ethical leadership in South African Public administration has not been an easy task due to the prevailing high rate of reported corruption, unethical practices, and political interference in local government. A study conducted by Chene (2012:2) found that public officials in local government are often caught on the wrong side of the law for unethical practices. The author also notes that local municipalities in South Africa are often confronted by undue influence from political authorities, which disrupts their decision-making processes. Malan and Smit (2001:15) make an important point that the ongoing corruption activities and maladministration result in the misuse of public resources, which in turn will have a hugely adverse effect on the development of the economy. Mafunisa (2003:87-94) pointed out the concern regarding the cadre policy and development strategy by the African National Congress (ANC). The policy jeopardized the state's capacity for service delivery as cadre deployment lacked skills and administrative expertise.

The above reflections highlight a clear picture that indeed local government is faced with challenges, and this poses a serious risk in the delivery of public services and also affects the economy and development of the country beginning with "Effectiveness" has indeed been undermined by poor governance by those trusted with the responsibility to govern, lack of effective systems in place to fight corruption, unethical practices, maladministration, thus this challenge are not tucked this will hinder prospects of good governance. We argue that the South African local government cannot be seen as a fully effective government if it is not prepared to consider the poor working relationship between leaders and followers. These challenges, which have been overlooked by many scholars, are the basis of our argument that for leaders to be declared as ethical leaders they should possess ubuntu within them as this will attribute humanity, care, and generosity and it will lead to sound working relationship between the leader and followers which intend make them to share a common goal in service delivery and eradicating the above mentioned challenges, We should always remember that employees performance better where there is common understanding emanating from good working relationship which is the most vital engine of this paper.

Theoretical Support of the Study

The paper is supported by the African Philosophy of Ubuntu, the

conceptual basis for a good working relationship between leaders and followers is driven by Ubuntu. The doctrine of facts in argument, the researchers argue that a leader without ubuntu to their followers is likely to jeopardize the level of performance, service delivery, and good governance. The view that the researchers have that encompasses the validity of the moral problem is that while ubuntu is tested among leaders, this motivates a change in behavior or performance among followers, and this brings a good working relationship between the leader and followers. The approach of leaving out this theory is very costly, as it undermines the public's confidence as taxpayers. Ubuntu has always been called the cradle of humanity; unfortunately, this approach has been misunderstood and misinterpreted, and if left alone, it will mainly cause confusion to many writers for overlooking and not understand that the dictatorship of the word ubuntu carries more power necessary for a leader to ensure that African values which bring, love, care, humanity and generosity to followers. Tutu (2004:25) refers to Ubuntu as an ideological concept that means a person is a person through other persons. Therefore, no one comes into this world fully formed. The author further adds that we would not be able to think, walk, speak, or even behave as human beings without seeing other human beings; we need to be human beings to be human. Therefore, in illustrating ethical leadership in the light of Ubuntu, Tutu (2005:27) writes that according to "Ubuntu, it is not a great good to be successful through being aggressively competitive and succeeding at the expense of others. In the end, our purpose is social and communal harmony and well-being. Ubuntu does not say, I think, therefore I am." It says rather, "I am a human because I belong, I participate, and I share." Harmony, friendliness, community, and great good, anything that subverts or undermines this sought-after good is to be avoided like the plague". As correctly defined by Khoza (2012:80) Ubuntu is spiritual but practically in its application." In making sense of this, the author highlights that humanity, kindness, and generosity really depend on each other; therefore, the need for caring from leaders and having humanity is a spiritual intent. Basically, this theory advocates for improved governance, and it rejects poor working relationships, as it examines leaders' humanity and the enactment of ethical leadership under a theoretical lens.

Making Sense of the Use of Ubuntu and Understanding its Value: Ethical Leadership and Good Governance in the Local Government Context

Ethical leadership and good governance are the two concepts that are prerequisites for achieving development in local government. Mapaya, Mukonza, and Shopola (2024:242) correctly cite Max Sisulu (2013) the former speaker of the democratic parliament in South Africa, arguing that achieving good governance requires strong mechanisms from the legislative sector. Therefore, we shift a little bit of this sense by putting a new perspective that is not all about implementing new mechanisms and tools for ethical leadership and good governance, but this has to do with whether those entrusted with good responsibility have a good relationship with their followers by achieving this will lead to good governance hence we advocated above that the theoretical lens for governing this paper is to use the African Philosophy of Ubuntu to clearly achieve ethical leadership and good governance. The overabundance of literature as empirically designed in understanding confirms that the challenges

facing the municipalities are mainly due to corruption and unethical practices, but what about the Ubuntu by leadership? This is the question that should be explored further in the field of public administration and affairs. We cannot be a well-developed state while we set aside the Ubuntu, as this is a prerequisite for ethical leadership and good governance. The question informs the discussions below.

Why Ubuntu is Important within the Public Sector

Ubuntu has always been called the cradle of humanity, unfortunately, this approach has been misunderstood and misinterpreted, and if left alone, it will be mainly cause confusion to many writers for overlooking and understand that the dictatorship of the word ubuntu carries more power necessary for a leader to ensure that African values which bring, love, care, humanity and generosity to followers. The Auditor-General South Africa (AGSA) (2022-2023) and (2023-2024) gives a clear picture of evidence that municipalities have consistently failed to produce clean audits. Therefore, it can be deduced based on this information that municipalities are struggling to achieve clean audits due to poor performance that emanates from the leadership. Leaders should take the lead in sharing blame, as without ubuntu, a poor working relationship is likely to jeopardize the quality of service delivery and the performance of followers. The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 - Chapter 7 of the Local Government, cements the objectives that municipalities should adhere to; therefore, we argue that without a stronger leadership that has ubuntu, this objective will be pointless.

Finding and Analysis Discussion on Ethical Leadership and Good Governance

Many African countries, including South Africa, have been experiencing many challenges such as corruption, unethical practices, bribery, fraud, and nepotism in the new democratic dispensation. In so saying, the media outbreaks and scholarly investigations have revealed that municipalities are viewed as one of the most affected. The final remarks made by various scholars, such as Kanyane, Houston, and Sausi (2013:130) have established the fact that generally South African public institutions are facing challenges of poor governance, increased corruption, lack of accountability, and massive failures in planning. Chapter 10 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996) recognizes the need for effective leadership and professional ethics in the public sector. Furthermore, the new Public Service Regulation (July 01, 1999) recognizes the need for a code of conduct in the public sector. The National Development Plan vision of 2030 has provided insightful, effective plans contributing to a well-developed country. Besides the plans in place, we argue that without effective ethical leadership, these plans are likely not to succeed. Literature also agrees that South Africa is faced with unethical leadership challenges, and this undermines the tax money paid by the citizens of South Africa. Municipalities have a code of conduct for offices and municipal councilors but sadly, unethical practices seem to be getting worse, and this undermines public confidence, which then manifests in ongoing public protests for service delivery. Ngubane (2021:1). Gildenhuys (1991) has emphasized that unethical practices by municipal councilors and officials should demonstrate accountability to their decisions in line

with their duties. Therefore, this necessitates a wide range of new thinking to ensure that leaders are ethical and that they adhere to the code of conduct. As we started above that one thing that was always overlooked relating to studies that involve around the concept of ethical leadership is the lack of Ubuntu amongst leaders to which affects the working relationship between the followers and the leaders to poor governance of the delivery of public service. This affects the quality of the delivery of public services. We cite Aryati, Sidiro, Hadiwidjaji, and Noermijati (2018: 236) pointing out that Ethical leadership is associated with behavior, whereas at the same time, a leader can create a good organizational workplace. We concur with the above authors that the behaviors leaders exhibit is likely to affect the performance of their followers. If such behaviors involve the abuse of power, they can result in poor working relationships between followers and leaders. Despite all the effort made trying to professionalize ethical leadership to eradicate unethical practices and behavior by leaders in the public sector is still a problem in South Africa, and this is particularly evident as these challenges start with leaders and cascade to followers. Lameck (2022:83) agrees, stating that leaders are expected to serve as role models to their followers. This includes demonstrating the behavioral boundaries set within an organization and the values from which the employees can learn and translate them into actions.

Conclusion

The current study findings support the need to adopt Ubuntu as the driving force to ensure humanity amongst leaders to followers in South African Municipalities, as the closest government to the people of South Africa. Therefore, to allow the emergence of leaders to have the spirit of ubuntu amongst them, this will enhance effective ethical leadership, good working relationships, and good governance, which are the main critical factors that ensure the delivery of public services. We understand that most Municipalities in South Africa are faced with challenges that hinder the delivery of public services. The confirmation of media reports and Auditor reports has revealed that most municipalities are placed under administration. We also refer to Manyane (2023) Cementing the fact "Eight of 24 Municipalities placed under administration" Independent Online (IOL) 9 June 2023. Therefore, adopting the spirit of Ubuntu, this approach will provide a solution for good governance. The study's findings will not only be applied to municipalities but also across other spheres of governance, and should serve as a solution for other neighboring countries that have overlooked the concept of Ubuntu through the lens of ethical leadership, as it should not be separated. The Municipal Managers and Senior Managers play a leadership role in municipalities, and they should professionally manage the way they conduct themselves; they should activate the spirit of ubuntu to discourage poor working relationships between themselves and their followers. The study suggests that relevant parties, such as legislators overseeing the implementation of the code of conduct, should be linked with Ubuntu as it rejects poor working relationships that now result in poor governance. It doesn't matter what kind of organization, either the public sector or private sector, Ubuntu should be instilled amongst leaders if we are aiming to achieve our mandate.

In closing, the study suggests that South Africa's local government should effectively instill ubuntu amongst leaders as they are entrusted with the responsibility and accountability for the delivery

of public service; furthermore, this should be cascaded to all levels of management. The NDP 2030 vision cemented crucial aspects to build a vibrant society, a thriving economy, and an ambitious nation, and this can only be done if we have effective ethical leadership that demonstrates ubuntu to enhance good working relationships with its followers. This will penetrate and create a capable development state, and the NDP 2030 vision will be a reality, and good governance will be enhanced.

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